

THE ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE AMONG NURSING STUDENTS REGARDING PATIENT SAFETY

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Abstract

Background: Patient safety is an essential part of medical science. Nurses particularly are the initial responder, who took the responsibility of providing qualitative care to the patient, including assurance of patient safety. Knowledge of patient safety measure is mandatory for nurses and other health care providers.

Aim: The aim of the study is to assess the knowledge level of nursing students regarding patient safety.

Method: This is a descriptive study, where the participants were selected through convenient sampling technique. The questionnaire with two portion was distributed among nursing students, portion A contain demographic characteristics of the study participants, while portion B contain questions specific to patient safety.

Results: The data collected was analyzed through SPSS version 21. As inference from sociodemographic, total participants of the study was 150, out of which 75 were male and 75 were female. Majority of the participants had from BSN 2nd year (60), followed by BSN 1st year (50), and BSN 3rd year (40). Participants had high level of knowledge on general concept of safety including definition of patient safety, but had poor knowledge on specific concept (radiation overexposure, medication compliance) as a patient safety related concern.

Conclusion: Patient safety is an importance health issue that is the indicator of quality of care provided to the patient, and it must be highlighted on high scale, in order to ensure that the care received by the client is qualitative and does not harm the patient. This study concluded that half of the students had poor knowledge, while remaining students had acceptable level of knowledge regarding patient safety. Most of them were aware of general knowledge on patient safety, however some of them had poor level of knowledge in regards to even a general question on safety.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background:

Patient safety is a corner stone of nursing and medical care, and is considered the fundamental health care quality. In order to fulfill or maintain patient safety, education is the only tool to fill the requirements. According to some authority patient

safety has become one of the major concern in the establishment of health care policies around the world(Organization 2021). So, is due to its importance this study will help assess the knowledge of nursing students regarding patient safety, which is their essential responsibility while providing care.

Patient safety is introduced as the effort done to prevent harm to the patient as much possible during the provision of health care and the elimination of the risk of unnecessary injury, associated with health care, to an acceptable minimum (Organization 2021). It is the combination of system effectiveness and individual performances to minimize the unintended and intended risk to the patient as much as possible. As from others sources, safety can be defined as the absence of exposure to danger and protection against the occurrence or risk of injury or loss (Aven 2022). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), patient safety is the absence of potential or unnecessary damage to the patient associated with healthcare. Patient safety determine the quality of care provided, a health care provider, particularly nurse if ensure patient safety in all dimension like supporting patient emotionally, prevent medication error, and ensure physical protection from hazards, describing quality care results in patient satisfaction (Hannawa, Wu et al. 2022).

As from global statistics it is estimated that approximately out of ten one patient experience patient safety related issue (Organization 2021). If consider in hospital it is about 14th cause of global burden disease (Halinen, Tiirinki et al. 2024). A study from European citizens indicates that while receiving health care at hospital, they had face a problem with safety concern, suggesting their bad experience with it. the unsafe practice not only effect patient itself, but rather it results in other morbidities in hospital, which are costly like (i.e. pressure ulcers, hospital-associated infections, thromboembolism, medication error) (Dimitriadou, Merkouris et al. 2021). Because, all these concern results from patient safety are preventable, if we educated health care provider, including nurses effectively, we can induce patient safety concepts in all aspect into nursing students mind. Thus, this will improve the environment of quality care nursing, increases patient and family satisfaction, and results in the provision of evidence base practice.

This can never be underestimated that nurses are the main responder while provision of health care, including ensuring patient safety (Phillips, Malliaris et al. 2021). They make approximately 50% of the active health care workforce. Comparison to other health care professional's nurses plays a crucial role

in maintaining effective communication, and correct malpractice work flow. Particularly, undergraduate nursing education is an initial step to guide novice nurses regarding patient safety. Passage of nursing students through educational and organizational challenges expand the novice nurse's ability to improve their awareness, promoting collaborative teamwork, and results in information sharing, all these results in measure which ensure patient safety (Smith, DesRoches et al. 2022).

Knowledge of the nursing students is essential for ensuring patient safety. This is not only in dimension of physical safety (prevention of falls, removal of any physical hazard from patient surrounding), but in the domain of the prevention of medical error (which also is a main cause that is lethal to patient life). other than that providing patient emotional support is also component of patient safety, so is to prevent him/her from self-harm due to some psychiatric illness. Knowledge regarding all these domains mentioned are essential for the provision of effective nursing care.

Due to the importance of the issue mentioned, this study aimed to assess the knowledge level of the nursing students in Lahore, Pakistan. Comparatively to other health concern, patient safety is less highlighted in Pakistan. In Pakistan where as we know that health care services are limited due to staff shortage, fear of reporting error, inadequate staff training, and lack of national standards. Completion of the study will provide an insight regarding patient safety. The study will fill a gap that is not highlighted from many years, and based on data analysis, will provide an insight to any further study requirement.

1.2 Problem Statement:

Patient safety is a corner stone of nursing and medical care, and is considered the fundamental health care quality. In order to fulfill or maintain patient safety, education is the only tool to fill the requirements. According to some authority patient safety has become one of the major concern in the establishment of health care policies around the world (Organization 2021). So, is due to its importance this study will help assess the knowledge of nursing students regarding patient safety, which is their essential responsibility while providing care.

1.3 Significant of study:

This study will be helpful for nursing students to gain knowledge about patient safety. By analyzing nursing student's knowledge regarding patient safety, the findings may be used as an inference in other research studies.

1.4 Aim of the study:

The study aim is to assess the level of knowledge among nursing students regarding patient safety.

1.5 Research Objective:

To assess the knowledge level of nursing student regarding patient safety.

1.6 Research Question:

What is the level of knowledge among nursing students regarding patient Safety?

1.7 Operational Definition:

Knowledge will be assessing through an adopted, modify and translate questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of 14 items ranging on nominal scale. The response to a question are classified as yes and no. Participant who tick on yes will be given 1, while those who tick on no will be given 2 on SPSS. Total score may range from 0-14, with higher score indicating higher level of knowledge. The Knowledge level as classifies as up to 33% will be considered Poor level of knowledge, 75% will indicates Acceptable level of knowledge and score more than 75% will be considered Good level of knowledge.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The present study aim is to assess the knowledge level of nursing students regarding patient safety. As we know that patient safety is an essential for quality care provision and patient, family satisfaction. Nurses plays a crucial role in the provision of care, including ensuring patient safety. Undergraduate nurses required special education and hands on practice for the provision of qualitative care. here are some previous studies mentioned conducted on the same topic, all of which arise the need for further investigation.

As inference from previous studies, a study with cross sectional approach was conducted in in Cyprus

and Greece. The study aimed to assess the level of knowledge among undergraduate nursing students of 3rd and 4th year regarding patient safety. The subject was analyzed through a specific questionnaire Health Professional Education Patient Safety Survey (H-PEPSS). The study concluded that there is a gap between theoretical knowledge and practice, and emphasized the need for effective collaboration between theory and practice. While, the knowledge of the students in the technical aspects of patient safety was higher, but had a poor knowledge about the sociocultural aspects of the patient, such as working in teams(Dimitriadou, Merkouris et al. 2021).

Similarly, another study conducted on nurses in Jordan. The aim of which is to assess the level of knowledge, attitude, and practice among nurses regarding patient safety. Participants were analyzed through convenient sampling. Total subject of the study was 307. The study was done between August 2022 and October 2022. As from results portion of the study, 59% of participants reported good knowledge about patient safety. 61% of participants reported positive attitudes toward patient safety. However, because this study was conducted on experienced nurses, not on students, so even 59% knowledge in such case were also consider poor. Based on findings it is recommended to implement educational program and training session to improve knowledge of nurses regarding patient safety(Ayyad, Baker et al. 2024).

A study done in South West Ethiopia. The purpose of which is to examine the knowledge, attitude, practice, and factors associated with patient safety practice among undergraduate health science students at Jimma University Institute of Health. A cross sectional study design was used from May to November 2021. Total participants of the study were 668. The results were contradiction to the above mentioned studies, knowledge of the students were comparatively good, while only 135 students had good practice regarding patient safety. So based on findings, it was concluded that students had poor practice regarding patient safety, while half of the students had good knowledge about patient safety. Here poor patient practice was due to the less durational attachment of students in clinical areas, the study year, and the knowledge of patient safety.

The study recommend patient safety related courses induction into the curricula of undergraduate health sciences students(Mohammed, Woldearegay et al. 2023).

A cross sectional study conducted in Ethiopia. The study was done on nurses working at Asella Referral and Teaching Hospital. The goal of the study was to investigate Knowledge, attitude, practice and associated factors towards patient safety. Total nurses included was 172. The data were collected from nurses from December 28, 2020 to January 05, 2021 by using a pretested questionnaire. Majority of the study subject were female (94). The majority 133(77.3%) of them were qualified for degrees and above. However, the nurse had a good knowledge 58.7% regarding patient safety. The study revealed that half of the students had good knowledge and had positive attitude towards patient safety. Educational programs and training on patient safety may need to take place for nurses to abate these problems(Wake, Tuji et al. 2021).

Another study conducted in the University of Gondar Comprehensive Specialized Hospital, Northwest Ethiopia. The objective of the study was to assess the patient safety culture and associated factors among health-care providers at the University of Gondar comprehensive specialized hospital, Northwest Ethiopia, 2020. Participants were selected through stratified simple sampling technique. Total participants were 575. 12 different safety culture related questions were analyzed. The overall level of positive patient safety culture was 45.3%. it was concluded that overall level of positive patient safety culture was low. Some of the factors mentioned in the study (working hour, experience, training) were significantly associated with the patient safety culture(Ayisa, Getahun et al. 2021).

Hence the above studies mentioned, indicate the need for further investigation regarding patient safety. There is some contradiction where higher level of knowledge was noted, that was due to participant’s qualification level. in such case this study aimed to assess knowledge among undergraduate nursing students. Knowledge at such stage is mandatory, because any negligence may lead to disrupt patient safety.

METHODOLOGY

1: Study Design:

□ A descriptive cross-sectional research study design was used.

3.2: Setting:

□ The study setting was Superior university department of nursing Lahore.

3.3: Sampling technique:

□ Convenient sampling technique is used.

3.4: Sample size:

□ The simple size is calculated through slovin’s formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

where

n= Sample size

N= Population size

e= Level of precision/margin of error

3.5.: Eligibility criteria:

3.5.1: Inclusion criteria:

- Students of BSN(Generic)
- Students of Superior University department of nursing Lahore only

3.5.2: Exclusion criteria:

- Post RN Students
- Graduated Nurses
- Others medical Health care workers

3.6: Ethical consideration:

The ethical consideration was followed which is set by committee of nursing department, superior university. Participants will ensure for data privacy and they are not forced to participate in this study. Participants were given enough information regarding study and their participation in this study.

There was no harm. Therefore, confidentiality were maintained.

3.7: Data collection tool:

Data was gathered by using an adapted version of tool to assess the level of knowledge regarding patient safety among nursing students.

3.8: Data collection procedure:

Data was gathered from nursing students of superior university department of nursing Lahore.

3.9: Population of study:

Our study population were nursing students of superior university department of nursing Lahore.

3.10: Duration of the study:

The study was taken approximately in 9 months.

4 RESULTS

Sociodemographic Characteristics of Participants

Table No: Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	75	50.0	50.0	50.0
Valid Female	75	50.0	50.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 1

As shown in the above table #1 the frequency & percentage of Male & Female included in the study. Which indicates that, out of 150 subjects 75(50%) were Male and the same as 75(50%) of the participants were Female.

Table No: 2 Educational Status of the Participants

	Freq uency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
BSN(Generic) 1st year	50	33.3	33.3	33.3
BSN(Generic) 2nd	60	40.0	40.0	73.3

Valid				
year	40	26.7	26.7	100.0
BSN(Generic) 3rd				
year	150	100.0	100.0	
Total				

Fig:2

As shown in the above table #2 & Fig #2 the educational level of Participants. The frequency &

Educational status

Percentage of study participants by educational level respectively are; BSN(Generic) 1st year 50(33.3%), BSN(Generic) 2nd year 60(40.0%), and BSN(Generic) 3rd year is 40(26.7%).

Nursing Students knowledge regarding Patient Safety

Table NO: 3

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	94	62.7	62.7	62.7
Valid	56	37.3	37.3	100.0
No				
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 3

Patient safety was designed to avert and decrease risks, errors and harms that happen to the patient during the delivery of health care.

As shown in the above table #3 the subject responses to question that “patient safety was designed to avert and decrease risks, errors, and harms that happen to the patient during the delivery of health care”. The frequency of subjects who responds correctly(yes) is 94(62.7%), while those who responds incorrectly (No) is 56(37.3%).

Table: 4

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	104	69.3	69.3	69.3
Valid No	46	30.7	30.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 4

Patient Safety is a sub-specialty in healthcare that developed with the growing advancement in health care systems

As shown in the above table & Fig #4 subjects response to question “Patient Safety is a sub- specialty in healthcare that developed with the growing advancement in health care system”. Majority of the subject responds correctly(yes) is 104(69.3%), while some of the subject responds incorrectly(No) is 46(30.7%).

Table No: 5

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	99	66.0	66.0	66.0
Valid No	51	34.0	34.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 5

As shown in above table #5, the subject responses to question (3) that “Errors,” “deviations” and “Errors,” “deviations” and “accidents” are components of patient Safety

“accidents” are components of patient Safety”. Once again majority of the subjects responds correctly(yes) is 99(66%), while small number of the subjects responds incorrectly(No) is 51(34%) out of 150 subjects.

Table No: 6

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	93	62.0	62.0	62.0
Valid No	57	38.0	38.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 6

Medication errors are patient safety issue and are one of the leading causes of injury and avoidable harm in health care systems.

As shown in the above table & Fig #6, the participant responses to question that “Medication errors are patient safety issue and are one of the leading causes of injury and avoidable harm in health care system”. The frequency of participant who responds correctly (yes) is 93(62%), and those who responds incorrectly (No) is 57(38%).

Table No: 7

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	90	60.0	60.0	60.0
Valid No	60	40.0	40.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 7

Unsafe injections practices are component of patient safety in health care settings and can transmit infections, including HIV and hepatitis B and C.

As shown in the above table #7 subject responses to question “Unsafe injections practices are component of patient safety in health care settings and can transmit infections, including HIV and hepatitis B and C”. The number of participant who responds correctly (yes) is 90(60%), while those who responds incorrectly (No) is 60(40%) out of 150 subjects.

Table No: 8

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	81	54.0	54.0	54.0
Valid No	69	46.0	46.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Fig:8

The above table & Fig #8 show Subject responses to question “Patient safety is the inhibition of adverse outcomes or injuries stemming from the processes of health care.”

Patient safety is the inhibition of adverse outcomes or injuries stemming from the processes of health care.

outcomes or injuries stemming from the processes of health care”. The number of subjects who responds correctly (Yes) is 81(54%), while those who responds incorrectly (No) is 69(46%).

Table No: 9

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	94	62.7	62.7	62.7
Valid No	56	37.3	37.3	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 9

Unsafe surgical care procedures are patient safety challenge and can complicate up to 25% of patients.

As shown in the above table & Fig #9, the subject response to question “Unsafe surgical care procedures are patient safety challenge and can complicate up to 25% of patients”. The frequency of subject who responds correctly (yes) is 94(62.7%), while the number of subject who responds incorrectly (No) is 56(37.3%).

Table No: 10

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	94	62.7	62.7	62.7
No	56	37.3	37.3	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 10

Diagnostic errors can occur in up five percent of adults in outpatient environment and are patient safety issue.

This table & Fig#10 show subject response to question “Diagnostic errors can occur in up five percent of adults in outpatient environment and are patient safety issue”. Majority of the subject responds correctly (yes) is 84(56%), while minor number of them responds incorrectly (No) is 66(44%) out of 150 subject.

Table No: 11

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	94	62.7	62.7	62.7
Valid No	56	37.3	37.3	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 11

As shown above in the table #11, the subject response to question “Unsafe blood transfusion practices put patients at risk of adverse blood transfusion reactions and the spread of infections”. Majority of the subject responds correctly (Yes) is 94(62.7%), while other responds incorrectly (No) is 56(37.7%).

Table No: 12

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	78	52.0	52.0	52.0
Valid No	72	48.0	48.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 12

As shown above in the table #13 participant response to question” Radiation mistakes include

Radiation mistakes include overexposure to radiation and incidence of wrong-patient and wrong-site identification.

overexposure to radiation and incidence of wrong-patient and wrong-site identification”. The frequency of the Subject who responds correctly (yes) is 78(52%), while the remaining participant responds incorrectly (No) is 72(42%).

Table No: 13

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	96	64.0	64.0	64.0
Valid No	54	36.0	36.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 13

The above table & Fig#13 shows the participant response to question “One of the very common and avoidable causes of patient injury in our hospitals is Venous thromboembolism

causes of patient injury in our hospitals is Venous thromboembolism”. Majority of the Participant responds correctly (yes) is 96(64%), while some of them responds incorrectly (No) is 54(36%).

Table No: 14

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	85	56.7	56.7	56.7
Valid No	65	43.3	43.3	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 14

As shown above in the table #14, the subject response to question “Patient safety is a central principle and significant actions must be taken to avoid any adverse events”. 85(56.7%) of the subject responds correctly (yes), while 65(43.3%) of them responds incorrectly (No).

Table No: 15

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	105	70.0	70.0	70.0
Valid No	45	30.0	30.0	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 15

As shown in the above table & Fig #15, the subject responds to question (13). Majority of the subject responds

Patient safety is when there is non-occurrence of avertible harm to a patient while receiving health care and decline of risk of needless harm related with health care to a tolerable level.

correctly (yes) is 105(70%), while minor number of the participant responds incorrectly (No) is 45(30%) out of 150 participants.

Table No: 16

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	100	66.7	66.7	66.7
Valid No	50	33.3	33.3	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 16

Regular hand washing is the most essential action to prevent healthcare related infections

As shown above in the table & Fig #16 participant response to question (14) that is “Regular hand washing is the most essential action to prevent healthcare related infections”. Which indicates that majority of the subject responds correctly (yes) is 100(66.7%), while remaining of the participant responds incorrectly (No) is 50(33.3%) out of 150 total participants.

Distribution of study participants by Sociodemographic Characteristics Table No: 1 Gender

Gender	Frequency (%)
Male	75(50.0%)
Female	75(50.0%)
Total	150(100%)

Table No: 2 Educational Status of Study Participant

Educational Level	Frequency (%)
BSN(Generic) 1 st Year	50(33.3%)
BSN(Generic) 2 nd Year	60(40.0%)
BSN(Generic) 3 rd Year	40(26.7%)

Table No: 3 Distribution of Participant based on knowledge score regarding patient safety

Knowledge Questions	True (%)	False (%)
Patient safety was designed to avert and decrease risks, errors and harms that happen to the patient during the delivery of health care.	94(62.7%)	56(37.3%)
Patient Safety is a sub-specialty in healthcare that developed with the growing advancement in health care systems.	104(69.3%)	46(30.7%)
“Errors,” “deviations” and “accidents” are components of patient Safety.	99(66%)	51(34%)
Medication errors are patient safety issue and are one of the leading causes of injury and avoidable harm in health care systems.	93(62%)	57(38%)
Unsafe injections practices are component of patient safety in health care settings and can transmit infections, including HIV and hepatitis B and C.	90(60.0%)	60(40.0%)
Patient safety is the inhibition of adverse outcomes or injuries stemming from the processes of health care.	81(54.0%)	69(46.0%)

Unsafe surgical care procedures are patient safety challenge and can complicate up to 25% of patients.	94(62.7%)	56(37.3%)
Diagnostic errors can occur in up five percent of adults in outpatient environment and are patient safety issue	84(56%)	66(44%)
Unsafe blood transfusion practices put patients at risk of adverse blood transfusion reactions and the spread of infections.	94(62.7%)	56(37.3%)
Radiation mistakes include overexposure to radiation and incidence of wrong-patient and wrong-site identification.	78(52.0%)	72(48.0%)
One of the very common and avoidable causes of patient injury in our hospitals is Venous thromboembolism	96(64.0%)	54(36.0%)
Patient safety is a central principle and significant actions must be taken to avoid any adverse events.	85(56.7%)	65(43.3%)
Patient safety is when there is non-occurrence of avertible harm to a patient while receiving health care and decline of risk of needless harm related with health care to a tolerable level.	105(70.0%)	45(30.0%)
Regular hand washing is the most essential action to prevent healthcare related infections	100(66.7%)	50(33.3%)

DISCUSSION

The purpose of recent study is to assess the knowledge level among Nursing students regarding patient safety. According to the current findings, total number of students in our study was 150, half of them were female 75(50.0%) and others half students were male. Their literacy level respectively was; 50(33.3%) BSN(Generic) 1st Year, 60(40.0%) BSN(Generic) 2nd year, and 40(26.6%) of the students was from BSN(Generic) 3rd Year.

The accuracy rate towards a questions related to patient safety were variable, somehow poor, and at the same time to some questions knowledge level was noted acceptable. The study revealed that majority of participants has low level of knowledge 72(48.0%) about a question “Radiation mistakes include overexposure to radiation and incidence of wrong-patient and wrong-site identification”. Followed by wrong answers 69(46.0%) to a question that “Patient safety is the inhibition of adverse outcomes or injuries stemming from the processes of health care”. Approximately half of the study participant 65(43.3%) did not have idea that “Patient safety is a central principle and significant actions must be taken to avoid any adverse events”.

When asked about a question that “Diagnostic errors can occur in up five percent of adults in outpatient environment and are patient safety issue” 66(40.0%) out of 150 students responds incorrectly. Similarly, while response to some questions specific to patient safety definition, it was seemed that the highest proportion of students 105(70.0%) was known about a question that “Patient safety is when there is non-occurrence of avertible harm to a patient while receiving health care and decline of risk of needless harm related with health care to a tolerable level”. it means that comparatively to a specific concept on patient safety knowledge were noted high, but general questions related patient safety participants had low level of knowledge. the highest response of accuracy is then to a question 104(69.3%) that “Patient Safety is a sub-specialty in healthcare that developed with the growing advancement in health care systems”. Similarly, the highest proportion of participant 100(66.7%) response correctly to a question related to hand washing that “Regular hand washing is the most essential action to prevent healthcare related infections”.

As comparatively to others study conducted on the same issue, the findings had variable level of contradiction. A descriptive comparative study was conducted with three and four-year undergraduate nursing students from the Cyprus Republic and Greece. A specific questionnaire was used which is known as Health Professional Education Patient Safety Survey (H-PEPSS) to describe students' knowledge in the classroom and clinical setting. The study outlined that there is a gap between theory and practice that disrupt the qualitative care concept such as patient safety. It was found that students had higher level of knowledge with the technical aspect of patient safety, while they had insufficient knowledge regarding its other essential component(Dimitriadou, Merkouris et al. 2021).

Another study with contradiction results was conducted on Nursing students. The objective of which it to determine the knowledge level of nursing students at a public university in the interior of the State of São Paulo about patient safety. This was a quantitative, cross sectional study which was done between May and June 2011. Total subject of the study was 118, which were enrolled in the third, fourth and fifth year. The study concluded that the students had the capability of ensuring patient safety and had a potential to achieve safe care, maintain qualitative care environment. Acceptable level of knowledge with nursing students in this study is due to the effort of teacher and students personal interest(Bogarín, Zanetti et al. 2014).

Another study was conducted on students at Urmia University of Medical sciences, West Azerbaijan province, Iran. This is cross sectional study approach which was done in 2012. Total of 134 students were participated. The purpose of the study was to assess the students' perception, and knowledge regarding patient safety. A specific questionnaire was used, the data collected is then analyzed through SPSS version 16.0. a total of 121 out of 134 participants actively engaged in the data collection process. It was concluded that approximately half of the study participants had good knowledge level, reflecting overall turnover of knowledge level insufficient. The findings of the study recommend educational program conduction

and further studies to highlight the same topic, thus to ensure patient safety(Nabilou, Feizi et al. 2015).

A study from Jordan conducted on nurses. The goal of which is to assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice among nurses regarding patient safety. This effort was done between August 2022 and October 2022. As from the results portion of the study, 59% of nurses had good level of knowledge, but for nurses 59% of knowledge regarding patient safety was insufficient. The study recommends training and educational activity conduction to improve nurse's knowledge regarding patient safety, as nurses are the initial responder at hospital, so their full control over patient safety related concern is mandatory (Ayyad, Baker et al. 2024).

Conclusion:

Patient safety is an importance health issue that must be highlighted on high scale, in order to ensure that the care received by the client is qualitative and does not harm the patient. This study concluded that half of the students had poor knowledge, while remaining students had acceptable level of knowledge regarding patient safety. Most of them were aware of general knowledge on patient safety, however some of them had poor level of knowledge in regards to even a general question on safety.

Limitation of the study:

Due to privacy disclosure concern some of the students were not interested in data collection process.

Recommendation:

The study based on findings recommend the;

- conduction of educational program and training session on patient safety.
- The study emphasized the development of research studies on the same concern.

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